

PROCESSING AND NEUTRALIZATION OF WASTE FROM HOUSEHOLD AND INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.

Farmanova Fatima Fakhriddinovna,

Bukhara State University 2-1 eco-20 Group student, ffarmonova1@gmail.com

Akhmedova Zebiniso Jamshid qizi

Bukhara State University 2-1 eco-20 Group student,

Idiyeva Xadicha Fakhriddinovna

Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management 1st year Magister

Abstract: This article deals with processing and neutralization of waste generated from household and industrial enterprises, one of the most important problems at the moment.

Keywords: absorption, adsorption, recuperation, anthropogenic changes, flora, fauna, reductant.

ПЕРЕРАБОТКА И ОБЕЗВРЕЖИВАНИЕ ОТХОДОВ БЫТОВЫХ И ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ.

Фармонова Фатима Фахридиновна,

Студент 2-1 ЭКО-20 группы Бухарского государственного университета,

Ахмедова Зебинисо Джамшид кызы,

Студент 2-1 ЭКО-20 группы Бухарского государственного университета,

Идиева Хадича Фахридиновна

Бухарский институт управления природными ресурсами магистр 1 курса

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена переработке и обезвреживанию отходов, образующихся на бытовых и промышленных предприятиях, что является одной из наиболее важных проблем на данный момент.

Ключевые слова: поглощение, адсорбция, рекуперация, антропогенные изменения, флора, фауна, восстановитель.

INTRODUCTION: With the development of society all over the world, the impact of people on the environment changes. As development accelerates on all fronts, environmental problems in the biosphere also increase, become larger and begin to take refuge in living nature. Scientific and technological development, man - made Developments, chemical industry, atomic stations these are very favorable for human survival and lifestyle, but bring environmental risks to the development of nature and living organisms in it.

Humanity often, forgetting that it is also a part of nature, negatively affects nature, disrupting the balance in it, creating universal, regional, territorial and national environmental risks without thinking about it. The mother planet today needs treatment from human influence, poverty, hunger, continuous population growth, ur - banization, greedy use of Natural Resources, increased demand for water, earth, energy are striking the biosphere.

MAIN PART: In all industrialized countries, solid waste accumulates in very large quantities. In addition to polluting themselves, the surrounding environment, solid waste also keeps a very large area of land occupied. This land can be used as a yekin field to grow cultivated plants and produce useful products for humans.

Solids are not only polluting the atmosphere, but also they contain a second kind of useful substances, this substance can be extracted only with the help of processing - lash. When the solids are left standing for long, precipitation runoff will contaminate the immediate area. It is completely unsuitable for activating waste, very toxic gases and solid metals fly into the atmosphere with smoke. As a result of rain and snow falling on it, toxic substances are slowly absorbed into the soil, which also poison the groundwater.

It is impossible to plant plants in this place for a long time, even after the solid waste accumulates and becomes clean in places where it has remained for a long time. As long as the plant is planted, it is also impossible to eat those products. Because these plants carry most of the toxic substances with them through the soil ozu - qa substances. These soils are rich in iron, chromium, and other substances, or depending on which species is a solid waste.

Industrial waste content by state standard 12.1.007-76- agi is divided into four groups by Toxic Substances and pollution of the external environment: [1]

- 1) extremely dangerous;
- 2) very dangerous;
- 3) moderately dangerous;
- 4) slightly dangerous.

Group 4 includes those in which industrial waste does not contain toxic substances. This group of waste contains phosphates, marganets store mercury salts of zinc.

Group 3 enterprise waste risks human chayote by storing copper sulfate, ash acid salts of copper, chlorine salt of nickel, lead oxide, etc.in its composition. Group 2 includes Mercury, margimush, chromium, leaded nitrogen and other toxic substances that pose a threat to human life in the structure of enterprise waste it is considered very dangerous by its storage of salts. Industrial waste production according to its type of waste- it is divided into qindisi and recyclable waste. It is known that not all waste can be buried or burned, part of which is processed and the necessary substances in it are extracted. When solid waste is processed and disposed of according to its type, their use increases in the imcone.

For example, they are divided into :

- black and non-ferrous metal waste;
- waste of minerals-waste that stores ash, slag and coal; - waste of plastics and polymers;
- cotton
- waste of paper, wool, silk and synthetic fibers; waste that preserves rubber; asbestos
- storing waste; waste from windows and building materials; waste from wood processing;
- waste from windows and building materials; waste generated in wood processing;
- skin and fur waste;
- food industry waste;
- waste of agricultural products; waste of paper and cardboard products;
- worn rubber and asbestos preservatives; plastic waste;
- wood products from consumption;
- failures of various iron metal;

- products of Solid Waste Treatment Devices and facilities. As can be seen from the above, part of them is completely destroyed by burial, but part is processed and a second mah - sulot is obtained. So, since there is also this type of waste in the industry of our republic, it is necessary to use the best ways to neutralize them, bring them to an environmentally harmless state and industrial it is necessary to strive to create a waste-free product technology at the enterprise.

Enterprise waste is divided into two, that is, one can be used, the second type cannot be used at all. From the waste of an industrial enterprise, bricks, building materials, fuel products are extracted, as well as certain elements in their pure form. For example, if the slag residues emitted in the oil refining industry are processed, then 1 million. of the tonnage, 4,300 tons of cob can be obtained.[2]

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY: The variety of problems studied in ecology requires the use of various methods. The following methods are used in ecology: field, laboratory, experimental and mathematical modules.

THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH CARRIED OUT: Metallurgical Combinator develops energy from slag and heat- what are the cement, fertilizer, material fibers from ash from the sections of the chimney is produced. Also, acid-resistant insulation from them devices for pouring materials and concrete are prepared. Unusable, hazardous to man and nature, waste is neutralized and buried in absolutely distant places from settlements. In special furnaces when neutralizing waste by a thermal method, they are burned at $1000+1200^{\circ}\text{C}$, but if toxic gases are formed from their combustion, they are definitely caught using special holders.[3]

Waste MiG - drugs from the Almaliq and Angren industrial enterprises in US are greatly increased. Sometimes the amount of waste collected is 40 million. it can reach up to tons, many of the waste in these enterprises will be recycled or buried. The highly toxic waste is trapped in iron containers 10 mm or 1 cm thick and buried in concreted pits on four sides, the pits reserved for waste are buried with concrete on all sides and soil on the edges. The concreted deep ground remains at least 80-100 cm below.[4]

In large cities, industrial waste comes out in huge numbers. For example, in the city of Moscow, one of the largest cities, solid, household waste costs 300 kg per person per year. Of this, paper and cartons are 28.8%; metal bodies are 5.7%; food waste is 28.5%; plastic is 5.1%; textiles is 3.1%; glass is 4.4%; fuel materials are 1.8%; inert materials are 3.4%; fine dust waste is 19.2% of the waste volume[5]

In our republic, solid waste is mainly ash and slag from energy - giving in-shoots; slag from black and non-ferrous metallurgy. Coke residues; dust waste from the coal - mining industry: sawdust and scraps from wood-processing farms; chemistry is formed from sa-noate in the form of phosphogips.

Solid waste contains a variety of chemicals, ranging from highly toxic substances such as arsenic, fluorine, phosphorus, mercury to inert substances, such as chalk, gypsum and clays.

The main factors that pollute the atmospheric air are industrial enterprises, chemical plants and factories, vehicles. Also, steel smelting furnaces, domna kilns, Coke-chemical industry, nitrogen-fertiliser plants, coal and non-ferrous metal mines, rail transport vehicles throw continuous toxic substances into the atmosphere.

Mining now mainly involves blasting, with large amounts of dust spreading to the environment as a result of the explosion. At high temperatures, a swarm of gases and dust forms in domna furnaces, these powders and gases contain 35-50% iron, 4-14% is gas, 8-13% silicon and aluminum, magnesium, calcium and other oxides.[6]

In Marten ovens, steel is melted at a high temperature, at this time a very large amount of sulfur oxide, nitrogen briquettes and is gas are thrown into the mosphera. 6-10 kg of dust in exchange for a ton of molten steel. 0.5-2.0 kg of IS gas, 0.5-1 kg of sulfate angdride, 1-2 kg of nitric oxide are formed.[7]

In the Republic, a number of GRESES spend in exchange for stoneware and mazut (including Angren, Tonkoron and Shirin in the city). Work incomplete burnt coal is considered a very polluting source of the atmosphere. This can also be seen from the following case. The temperature of heat in a non - woven furnace should be maintained at 600-700 °C from beginning to end.[8] If the temperature drops from this of course the stoneware cha - la burns, as a result of which a lot of CO, and water vapor are thrown into the air.

CONCLUSIONS: When a mixture of different gases increases in the composition of atmospheric air, this thing will definitely harm human health. If there is an increase in is gas from gases in the air, it is absolutely not felt by a person, this gas is extremely toxic and leads a person to death. It does not smell, which is why a person remains unaware of the presence of is gas when he breathes. In large industrialized cities, the air is incredibly heavy the stain can be noticed as soon as it enters the city. Navoi, Angren, more than 10 human health in the atmospheric air in the cities of Almaliq there are harmful gases for.

The danger of gassing is that they pass into the lungs and blood during the breathing process, accumulate with moisture in the mucous membrane and become inflamed, and eventually cause severe diseases. Gas inhalation causes an increase in lung cancer, aller - Gia, bronchial asthma, and respiratory diseases. Hence, when the air polluted areas become known, there are finding gas sources that can be thrown into the mosphera, you can clean them and it is necessary to try to throw fresh air into the mosfera as much as possible. A person can live only a few minutes without oxygen according to his structure, the most necessary thing in the process of survival is oxygen. Oxygen can contain only substances necessary for the human body and also often toxic substances.

According to data, sources of atmospheric pollution are considered below - GIS: energy 28.5%; non-ferrous metallurgy 21.6% ; qua metallurgy 15.2%; oil extraction 7.9%; oil refining 5.1%, 21.7% from the rest of the networks give toxic gases.[9] Gases that are thrown into the atmosphere can be solid, liquid, gaseous, non volatile-you, periodic, in a single large volume, supplied and disordered.

REFERENCES

1. Уиттэкер Р. Сообщества и экосистема. М.: Прогресс, 1981.
2. Федоров В.Д., Гильманов Т.Г. Экология. М.: Изд-во МГУ, 1980. С. 464.
3. Чернова Н.М., Былова А.М. Экология. М., Просвещение, 1988.
4. Шарова И.Х., Свешникова В.А. Проблемы экологической морфологии. М.: Знание, 1988.
5. Эргашев А.Э. Флора водорослей коллекторно-дренажной сети Голодной степи и ее значение. Ташкент: Фан, 1968.
6. Эргашев А.Э. Закономерности развития и распределения альгофлоры и искусственных водоемов Средней Азии. Ташкент, Фан, 1976. С.358.
7. Эргашев А.Э. Экологические особенности водорослей водоемов Средней Азии. Ташкент: Фан, 1979. С. 8-45.
8. Эргашев А.Э. Экология протококковых водорослей Средней Азии/Альгофлора и микофлора Средней Азии. Ташкент: Фан, 1979.
9. Яблоков А.В. Ядовитая природа. М.: Мысль, 1990. С. 124.
10. Яшнов В.А. Экология водных организмов. М.: Наука, 1966.
11. Elton Ch. Animal Ecology. New York, Macmillan, 2nd. ed. 1935; 3rd. ed. 1947.
12. Evans F.C. Ecosystem as the basic unit in ecology//Science. New York, 1963, p. 449.
13. Franklin R.T. Analysis of Temperate Forest Ecosystems. Springer-Verlag. New York, 1970. pp. 86-99.